

IMPACT OF MID DAY MEAL : SCHOOL LUNCH POLICY**Researcher****Laxmi Vijay Kasture***Ph.d student***Guide****Dr. Gorakh Dond****Associate Professor***Adv. Vasant Hande College of Education,
Nashik***ABSTRACT :**

The School lunch provides an important opportunity for learning healthy habits and well balanced school meals have been linked to improved concentration in class, better educational outcomes and fewer sick days. Many countries in the world have policies to help schools provide nutritionally balanced meals which also reflect the general eating culture of each nation. School lunch has brief history from 18th century. Since 1790 in Munich Germany Benjamin Thompson served first school lunch. United Kingdom published the first National Policy in 1941. Free School Meal, low cost school meal, income based criteria these are types of school meal in the World. Example Sweden, Finland, Estonia and India are among the few countries which provide free school meals to all pupils in compulsory education. Many countries provide meals to improve attendance rates. In India, all the Government school students are provided with the lunch through the 'MidDay Meal Scheme' with an objective of enrolment, retention, social inclusion, social interaction. MDM started in 1995. Though this study objectives of school lunch, financial provision, supplementary feeding, food distribution system, students good habits, courtesy, equipment supply these topics are focused. IN 2017 World Food Programme (WFP) implemented or supported school feeding programmes for 18.3 million children in 71 countries. WFP has been working with governments around the World for over 45 years.

Keywords : Mid Day Meal Scheme, School lunch Policy around the world, Countries, Education, Menu, Nutrition level. WFP.

INTRODUCTION :

Different types of school food programmes are organized all over the World. School Meal, School lunch, school breakfast, school dinner these programs are going on under different names. There are variety of food systems for primary and secondary education in all countries in Asia, Europe, United Kingdom, United Nations, USA.

History of School Lunch :

In 1790 in Munich Germany, Benjamin Thompson served the first school lunch. Since 1906 the school nutrition arrangements were changed from 1940 to 1990 from time to time. In 1933 a national school program was started by establishing a national level school in 1941 and was published in the National School Meal Policy in 1941 across the United Kingdom. This is the first policy which has set nutritional guidelines for school lunches, requiring balanced meals which include the appropriate levels of protein, fat and calories. In 1948 as a guarantee of basic education in Finland in every school for all students of primary and higher secondary education shared. In 1971 The French government established a guide policy for school menu. Since 1973 Spanish lunch Swedish got free elementary School in 1925. Madras Corporation was established during 1925 British Rule . India started Midday Meal in 1975 after Independence. Government of India integrated Child Development Program ICDS, Government Higher Secondary School, Anganwadi for the 1998 Government of India for the elementary education scheme and 1.6 million school beneficiaries in India. In Japan the were given attention after the World War II in 1952. IN the 1960s Iran started the free lunch under subsidy education program. IN 1954 it started preparing meals from primary to junior college. Till 2004 99% schools and 82% junior colleges had taken advantage. IN 2012 in Nigeria the statewide meal program was started in primary schools. This school history shows the since the 18th century, school lunch are continuously going on throughout the World.

OBJECTIVES OF SCHOOL LUNCH PROGRAM :

The purpose of school food aimed at different schooled is different. In developed countries it is a source of nutritious food. It is seen as an investment for the future as a national asset. In developing countries to encourage children to be educated in schools to promote education to create security and healthy citizens. School food is implemented as a solution to malnutrition and poverty. In India students attending regular school. Getting 100% registration aims to reduce the leakage in education. Also to enhance enrolment, retention and attendance of children in schools as well as improving their nutritional levels and to impart a spirit of equality.

FINANCIAL PROVISION FOR SCHOOL FOODS :

The system of financial provision, funding for school lunch is different across the World. IN the developed countries it depends on the financial condition of the parents. For example, in the united States, Germany, Canada where the needy children get a discounted rate of food, the children who have a lot of financial income have to pay the cost of food. In India , the policy does not differ as per the parents economic level. All children get free cost lunch, it is the Midday Meal. It is available for the Government and Government aided schools free of cost but not for the English medium schools. In Finland , Sweden all school meals are fully funded by the government. MDM Scheme in India is World's largest feeding programme reaching up to about 12 crore children; in 1.16 million schools. The Akshay Patra Foundation run serving meal to 1.4million children in India.

FODS AND SUPPLEMENTS :

United Kingdom, Finland, Sweden, Canada, Australia, England provide fruits, fruit juice, nutritious vegetables, salad, meat, egg, pulses, sprouts and dry fruits. Only Japan offers excellent lunch in Asia. India has a challenge because of the country's massive population.MDM Scheme provide rice, rice-dal, khichdi, curry.Biscuit and Rajgira Laddu are provided in India as a dietary supplement. It is challenge for India to full meal totally free of cost . A Spotlight has been turned on what children eat for lunch in the wake of raising obesity epidemic among the world's youth. Obesity can increase the risk of chronic diseases including diabetes, heart disease, stroke even some cancers. Canada nutritional guidelines suggest one third of the recommended dietary allowances of protein, Vitamin A, Vitamin C, Iron, Calcium and Calories must be provided. In dia provide 12 gram protein and 300gram calories in daily lunch through Midday Meal. However, milk, fruits, eggs are not included in the MDM. Parents and students are waiting for these items to be included and given to children.

FOOD DISTRIBUTION ARRANGEMENT :

Food distribution system is unique in many countries. A table chair meeting arrangement in most of the countries. China does not use chair, only tables are available because students waste easting food chatting without paying attention to the food and do not arrive early in classrooms. Japan has well thought off delivery systems in place. Students involvement is a method of self reliance habit. Every class meal is packed from large trolley. Class teacher and students group participate and distribute.Students bring table mat, cap, apron, brush toothpaste, napkins with them from home for

school lunch. Post their lunch they wash their plates, spoons and also clean the flooring if required. A dedicated 50 minutes recess is used for this work. However, in India students use playground, Corridor, classrooms for taking meal. Separate dining hall is yet missing in India. Soil and dust are present many times on classroom bench and floor where students sit to take lunch. Water is not enough for washing hands, plates. Also liquid hand wash/soap are not available. Student take food by standing in queue and sit in queue on the playground. Improvement in distribution is needed in India.

CLEANLINESS AND OTHER GOOD HABITS ETIQUETTES:

In cleanliness and other good habits other countries are far ahead of India. Kitchen, utensils are clean in other countries. India still lacks cleanliness. Students do not bring handkerchief in the bag in rural areas. In the cities students bring newspaper to spread on the floor and take food keeping on the newspaper. Many students do not observe etiquettes while having lunch. Rural areas face issues of shortage of drinking water and toilets. Indian Government tried to provide all facilities for the students but diversity in India's geographical situation is a major hurdle for the same. Right to Education is favorable for students. Under this rule many things are provided in school. India's massive population remains a challenge for cleanliness.

EQUIPMENT AND RAW MATERIALS :

World over equipment are used with modern technology. Cleaning of the tools is closely monitored. Grains, Pulses, Vegetables, fruits, milk etc. are obtained from the school's field. Many countries opt for biological techniques. Students actively participate in school's farm and gardens. In the United Nations obesity is a major problem so school farming vegetables are suggested. Deep fried foods are limited to not more than two portions per week. Example in Europe at least one portion of fruit and one portion of vegetables per day is compulsorily included. Some places like Denmark, Norway, Netherlands and Belgium do not have a compulsory system of school meals. Schools allow children to bring their own lunch from home. Even in India many students bring their lunch box from home especially in cities and government aided schools. In India School farms and gardens concept not present for cultivating vegetables/fruits for school lunch. Cook and helpers bring vegetables for that particular school from rural areas. Saving group (Bachchat Gat) bring vegetables in cities. But their bills and grants are not paid on time. So the Bachchat Gat ladies suffer for daily purchasing of vegetables. Government has given contract of vegetable supply to a contractor as that of a grains supplier. This is the prime reason for not using sufficient vegetables in daily Midday Meal in India. Daily protein requirement is not fulfilled, fruits like Banana are also not given in India. Only Dal Rice, Pulav are available every day.

The calorific and nutritional value and food norm per child per day are as mentioned in the below table :

	Primary	Upper Primary
Calorie	450	700
Protein	12	20
Rice /Wheat	100 gram	150 gram
Dal	20 gram	30 gram
Vegetables	50 gram	75 gram
Oil & fats	5 gram	7.5 gram

Micronutrients and de-worming medicines in convergence with school health programme of NRHM

DURATION OF LUNCH PERIOD :

A child should have atleast 30 minutes lunch period to get to the table and consume the meal properly. In Japan 50 minutes lunch period is given including time for cleaning and preparation. In India 25 to 30 minutes are available however it is not sufficient for Midday Meal. A minimum of 45 minutes is required.

WHAT GOES INTO BALANCED LUNCH ?

Balanced lunch include a variety of foods to help children get all the nutrients. India’s zero cost Midday Meal should be chargeable to students for fruits on a minimum cost or as per parents economic condition. This would help the Government to provide much nutritional food. Foods according to the geographical scenario in India. Example: Rice Fish curry in coastal area. This should be researched by studying the methods of school feeding in other countries of the World. In order to eliminate the shortcomings regional grains, crops and seasonal fruits should be incorporated in the Midday Meal. Today’s children are our National wealth for tomorrow. So provide them with nutritional food such as fruits , milk, eggs. Like other countries in India it is necessary to charge parents as per their income groups for minimum fees or cost for the meal in order to provide all items in the Midday Meal.

FUEL :

The fuel most widely used to make school meals is Solar energy in Western and Asian countries. LPG is provided in India but it is not easily available. Hence, traditional fuel method are used to prepare food using coal and wood fire. Solar and electric appliances using wind power, boiler, solar cooker must be used in Asian countries. India is the only country in Asia to run 12 crore student’s Midday Meal on zero cost from students. In Pakistan, Sri Lanka , Nepal World Food Programme (WFP) provide school lunch.

IMPACT OF MIDDAY MEAL IN INDIA :

The midday meal program (MDM) has had a positive impact in some selective cases (e.g enhancing enrolment, attendance and lowering, retention and dropout of students) which are essential for achieving the higher level of performance of students particularly belongs to BPL level residing in the rural areas. Some other benefits like removal of classroom hunger social and gender equality and

formation of good habits of students other than academic achievement in school. MDM can play a role in aerodin cast prejudice and nurturing a culture of social equality as students from different class and cast backgrounds share together. Midday meal give the childrens adequate nutritional support but the whole process took so much of time from normal teaching nad learning process that it resulted in a reason for spoiled academy environment in school. Teacher had faced the problem of indecipline and overburdening of workload.

Across the World school lunch nutrition standards are the basis for improving nutritional intake of all school children. However, this will only be successful if pupils like and choose to eat these meals. This is an aspect that has been largely neglected in the development of school meals till now. Therefore children are now being involved from the beginning of food service planning including taste. Parents too are encouraged to be involved in school meal policies. Changes in the dinning environment can also improve food choice, reduce queuing time and support social interactions. Importantly focus on school meals should aim towards health promotion.

REFERENCES :

1. Livsmedelsverket website skolmaltider section
2. www.oph.fi/download/47657.schoolmeal_in_finland.pdf
3. https://wikipedia.org/wiki/school_meal